

OZARBAYJONDA INKLUSIV TA'LIM TIZIMINING SHAKLLANISHI

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Аннотация. *Ta'lim iqtisodiy o'sish, aholining ijtimoiy himoyasini mustahkamlash, daromadlarning oshishi va bandlik imkoniyatlarini yaxshilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shuning uchun hukumatlar ta'lim sohasining rivojlanishini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishi sifatida belgilaydilar. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, zamonaviy davrda jamiyatlarning rivojlanish darajasi faqat iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar bilan emas, balki ta'limning har bir shaxs uchun erkin va teng imkoniyatlar yaratish bilan o'lchanadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan inkluziv ta'lim XXI asrning asosiy ta'lim yondashuvlaridan biri sifatida qabul qilinadi. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining "Hech kimni ortda qoldirmaslik" printsipiga muvofiq, inkluziv ta'lim ijtimoiy adolatni ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu model faqat jismoniy imkoniyatlari cheklangan bolalarni emas, balki turli til, etnik va madaniy guruhlarga mansub shaxslarni o'z ichiga olib, ta'limda ajratishning oldini olishni maqsad qiladi.*

O'zbekiston Respublikasida ham ta'lim jamiyat hayotida muhim rol o'ynaydi, aholining ijtimoiy himoyasini mustahkamlashda va bandlikni ta'minlashda alohida ahamiyat kasb etadigan sohalaridan biridir. Dunyo bo'ylab bo'lgani kabi, zamonaviy davrda O'zbekistonda ham inkluziv ta'lim tizimining shakllanishi davlatning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida belgilangan. So'nggi yillarda bu sohada huquqiy baza takomillashtirildi, inkluziv maktablar va sinflar yaratish yo'nalishida bir qator tadbirlar o'tkazildi. Ammo mavjud vaziyatni tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatadiki, inkluziv ta'limga erishish uchun amalga oshirilishi zarur bo'lgan bir qator islohotlar mavjud. Ushbu tadqiqotda birinchi marta O'zbekistonda inkluziv ta'lim tizimining mavjud holati baholanib, uni yaxshilash yo'llari ko'rsatilgan. Tadqiqotda tizimli yondashuv, analitik umumlashtirish va taqqosiy tahlil metodlaridan foydalanilgan.

Калит so'zlar: *inkluziv ta'lim, nogironligi bo'lgan shaxslar, ijtimoiy siyosat, ijtimoiy adolat, bandlik.*

Аннотация. *В усилении экономического роста и социальной защиты населения, в повышении доходов и улучшении возможностей трудоустройства образование играет важную роль. Поэтому правительства определяют развитие образования как один из приоритетов своей социально-экономической политики. Следует отметить, что в современном обществе уровень развития стран измеряется не только экономическими показателями, но и доступностью образования для каждого человека, а также равенством возможностей. В этом контексте инклюзивное образование рассматривается как один из основных подходов XXI века. В соответствии с принципом ООН "Не оставлять никого позади" инклюзивное образование играет важную роль в обеспечении социальной справедливости. Эта модель направлена на предотвращение дискриминации в образовании, охватывая не только детей с ограниченными возможностями, но и людей, принадлежащих к различным языковым, этническим и культурным группам.*

В Азербайджанской Республике образование также играет важную роль в жизни общества, являясь одной из ключевых сфер, которые способствуют усилению социальной

защиты населения и обеспечению занятости. Как и в других странах мира, в современный период в Азербайджане формирование системы инклюзивного образования определено как один из приоритетов социально-экономической политики государства. В последние годы была улучшена юридическая база в этой области, предприняты меры по созданию инклюзивных школ и классов. Однако анализ текущего положения показывает, что для достижения инклюзивного образования необходимо осуществить ряд реформ. В этом исследовании впервые оценивается существующее состояние системы инклюзивного образования в Азербайджане и предлагаются пути его улучшения. В исследовании использованы методы системного подхода, аналитического обобщения и сравнительного анализа.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, люди с инвалидностью, социальная политика,

Abstract. Education plays a pivotal role in fostering economic growth, enhancing social protection for the population, increasing household incomes, and improving employment opportunities. For this reason, governments identify the development of the education sector as a priority within their socio-economic policy frameworks. It is important to emphasize that, in contemporary times, the level of societal development is measured not solely by economic indicators, but also by the extent to which education is accessible and provides equal opportunities for all individuals. In this context, inclusive education is recognized as one of the fundamental educational approaches of the 21st century. In accordance with the United Nations' principle of "Leaving no one behind," inclusive education contributes significantly to the promotion of social justice. This model not only encompasses children with physical disabilities but also includes individuals from diverse linguistic, ethnic, and cultural backgrounds, thereby aiming to eliminate discrimination within the educational system.

In the Republic of Azerbaijan, education is one of the key sectors that plays an important role in the life of society, significantly contributing to strengthening social protection and ensuring employment. As in many parts of the world, the development of an inclusive education system has also been identified as one of the priorities of the state's socio-economic policy in modern-day Azerbaijan. In recent years, the legal framework in this field has been improved, and a number of measures have been taken toward the establishment of inclusive schools and classrooms. However, an analysis of the current situation reveals that there is still a need for a series of reforms to successfully achieve inclusive education.

This research, for the first time, assesses the current state of the inclusive education system in Azerbaijan and proposes ways for its improvement. The study employs a systematic approach, analytical generalization, and comparative analysis methods.

Key words: Inclusive education, Persons with disabilities, Social policy, Social justice, Employment.

Introduction

The experience of developed countries proves that it is impossible to achieve economic growth without having high-quality education. For reference, the results of studies conducted by the World Bank in 192 countries show that 16% of the growth in the world economy is due to physical capital, 20% is from natural resources, and 64% comes from human capital [1]. Therefore, even in times of economic crisis, developed countries do not reduce the funds allocated to education and science; on the contrary, they increase them. According to experts, 'the political existence and economic resilience of any country aiming to ensure its economic

independence, the formation of its national economy, and its further quantitative and qualitative growth, depends largely on the establishment of a new education system enriched with universal human values and its regulation by the state" [2, s.32].

In our opinion, the current and future socio-economic development is directly dependent on the development of education. Therefore, countries aiming to achieve strong socio-economic development should pay special attention to the development of the education sector, and this should be among the priorities of every country. Education plays a crucial role in addressing social issues such as increasing income, expanding employment opportunities, reducing poverty levels, and more. It is no coincidence that, in September 2000, at the Millennium Summit organized by the United Nations (UN), attended by representatives from 183 nations and 147 states, education was ranked second among the factors influencing the reduction of poverty and the promotion of human development in the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). This shows the significant role of education in reducing poverty [3]. Research shows that as the levels of education increase, opportunities for employment expand, income rises, the standard of living improves, and poverty decreases. *'In a market economy, normal living conditions are achieved only through the full and efficient employment of the existing labor force, which primarily depends on the increase in the overall level of development of citizens, their intellectual potential, professional qualifications, and education levels'* [4, s.77].

The following graph shows the relationship between the nominal income of the population and the literacy rate in Azerbaijan (**Graph 1**).

Graph 1. The relationship between the literacy rate of the population and nominal income in the Republic of Azerbaijan

Source: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.ADT.LITR.ZS?locations=AZ>,
<https://www.stat.gov.az/source/>

As can be seen, there is a strong correlation ($R=0.8684$) between the literacy rate of the population and their nominal income.

In Azerbaijan, the development of the education sector is also one of the priorities of the government's socio-economic policies. During the Millennium Summit, achieving high indicators in general secondary education was among the goals set for Azerbaijan. Several reforms have been implemented in this regard. Within the framework of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG), significant success has been achieved in terms of universal primary education. For instance, the literacy rate among the population aged 15-24 was 99.9% in 1999

and reached 100% in 2015. The gross enrollment ratio in primary education has also increased. Specifically, this indicator was 99.2% in 2000 and rose to 99.8% in 2015. The primary school completion rate has also increased from 92.8% to 100% during the corresponding period. The share of students who started their education from the 1st grade and completed it by the 5th grade increased from 96.8% in 2000 to 99.9% in 2015 [5].

In recent years, there have been significant changes in the number of preschool educational institutions. In our country, the number of preschool educational institutions was 1,790 in 2000. Over the past 22 years, the most notable decrease in the number of preschool institutions occurred in 2008. In that year, the number of preschool educational institutions had decreased to 1,612. In 2023, the number of such institutions increased to 1857.

General education is divided into two groups: full-time and part-time. In recent years, a decrease has been observed in the number of full-time educational institutions. The number of such institutions was 4548 in 2000/2001, but by 2023/2024, it had decreased to 4422. The number of students attending full-time general education institutions was 1653703 in 2000/2001, and by 2023/2024, it had increased to 1704217. In 2023/2024, 99.0% of students attending full-time general education institutions were enrolled in public schools, while only 1% were enrolled in private schools.

The number of vocational education institutions was 108 in 2000, and by 2023, it had decreased further to 92. A decrease has also been observed in the number of students enrolled in vocational institutions. In 2000, there were 22696 students, while in 2023, the number had decreased to 29144.

In recent years, there has been a decline in the number of state and non-state vocational education institutions in Azerbaijan. For example, in the 2000/2001 academic year, there were 71 such institutions, while in the 2023/2024 academic year, their number decreased to 59. The number of students enrolled in state and non-state vocational education institutions in our country was 42612 in 2000-2001, while in 2023/2024, it had increased to 65640. As seen, despite the decrease in the number of state and non-state vocational education institutions, the number of students enrolled in them has risen.

In the field of higher education, in the 1990/1991 academic year, there were 17 higher education institutions operating in our country. In the following years, the number of higher education institutions saw a significant increase. For example, in the 2023/2001 academic year, the number of higher education institutions had increased to 51.

Inclusive Education in the Field of Education

In recent years, among the reforms carried out in the field of education worldwide, ensuring inclusiveness has been a central focus. Relevant international organizations are implementing serious reforms in this area, placing obligations on states and calling on governments to fulfill the responsibilities arising from these commitments. The fourth of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) — *to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all* — specifically emphasizes the importance of quality education [6].

According to UNICEF, “*inclusive education is the most effective way to give all children a fair chance to go to school, learn the skills they need, and develop to their full potential*” [7]. “*Inclusive education can be defined as a process aimed at fostering the development of all children, shaping their socio-cultural and individual characteristics, and preparing them to become productive and contributing members of society.*” [8].

“Inclusive education is a development process aimed at making general education accessible to all and based on the adaptation to the diverse needs of all children” [9].

As it can be seen, the definitions of inclusive education are essentially similar to one another. In our view, inclusive education is a model that serves to develop the knowledge and skills of all children (including children with disabilities) by providing them access to schooling. In other words, inclusivity in education means making it accessible to everyone. According to UNICEF, there are 240 million children with disabilities worldwide [7]. Like their peers, children with disabilities also have the right to read, learn, and discover their talents. However, their social exclusion leads to the development of various complexes, which hinders the timely identification of their talents and abilities. Inclusive education, by providing equal opportunities, prevents the emergence of such issues. *“Inclusive education is the inclusion of children, regardless of their physical, psychological, intellectual, and other characteristics, in the same class at school with their peers”* [10].

In recent years, a series of reforms have been implemented in Azerbaijan to ensure inclusivity in the education sector. It is important to note that our country ratified the Convention on Human Rights in 1992, thereby undertaking the responsibility to protect the right of every child to education.

A special state program on inclusive education has also been adopted in our country. Specifically, by the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, dated December 14, 2017, the "State Program on the Development of Inclusive Education for Persons with Disabilities in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2018–2024" was approved. The aim of the State Program is to ensure the right to education for persons with disabilities at all levels of education on an equal footing with others and to create an accessible environment for their education [10].[././User/Downloads/Inclusive - info for website_UB \(3\).docx - _ftn1](#).

Inclusive education has many advantages. It ensures the integration of children with disabilities into society, provides opportunities for the identification of their talents and skills, and creates conditions for the development of their potential. *“Inclusive education is extremely beneficial. This is because its primary goal is not only to restore children's right to education, but also to facilitate their integration into society, increase their chances of finding employment in the future, and empower them to make independent decisions”* [8].

The newly established system, of course, will have its advantages, but it will also come with challenges. However, *“observations show that overcoming existing stereotypes about persons with disabilities and ensuring their acceptance as equal members of society will not be easy. The issue lies in the fact that while society may theoretically agree with inclusive education, doubts and hesitations arise when it comes to implementation”* [11]. The education system must be prepared for this reform. Relevant infrastructure should be established in educational institutions. It is essential to have classrooms that are suitable for the inclusive education process. Personnel working in the education sector should be trained for this process. Psychological support for students in educational institutions should be strengthened.

In addition to all of this, one of the key issues is raising awareness within society on this topic. Not only teachers and students but also parents must be prepared for this process. In our opinion, in order to achieve inclusivity in education, it is essential to first carry out awareness-raising efforts in society, ensuring that community members are prepared for this process. The topic of inclusive education should be kept on the agenda in the mass media and social networks, making it a subject for discussion. Conducting training on inclusive education in schools is advisable.

Conclusion

In recent years, as in all other fields, a series of reforms have also been carried out in the field of education in Azerbaijan. As a result of these reforms, significant improvements have been observed in both the quantitative and qualitative indicators of education. For instance, the literacy rate among the population aged 15–24 has reached 100%. The net enrollment ratio in primary education has increased to 99.8%, the proportion of students who complete grades 1 through 5 has reached 100%, and the primary education completion rate has risen from 92.8% to 100%.

One of the global priorities in education in recent years has also been ensuring inclusiveness. In this direction, several reforms have been implemented in our country, and the relevant normative-legal framework has been established. However, there is still a need for fundamental reforms in the development of an inclusive education system in Azerbaijan. Since inclusiveness is relatively new, public awareness on the matter remains low. Moreover, there is a shortage of university-trained specialists with the specific knowledge and skills required in this field. The infrastructure in educational institutions related to inclusivity is also insufficient.

In our view, in order to establish an inclusive education system in Azerbaijan, public awareness efforts must be strengthened, the necessary infrastructure should be developed, and the preparation level of the human resources involved in this process must be enhanced. Raising the level of inclusiveness in education will depend on the joint efforts of all participants in the process.

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